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Efficiency Assessment of H₃O® Smartomizer in Citrus

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Summary

The new generation of pesticide application sprayers developed by Pulverizadores Fede adjusts airflow and spray volume rate to the characteristics of the canopy and the target of the treatment. The aim of this work was to assess the efficiency of this new generation in citrus crop. Field trials were carried out to compare the new H₃O® S3.0 Sprayer with a Fede Futur 1000L 2005 as reference. Each trial consisted of spraying a tracer (brilliant sulfoflavine) in two central paths of the orchard. Results showed that the H₃O® sprayer was a highly efficient airblast sprayer. It reduced the power consumption by 55 %, the noise contamination by 15 dBA, and the potential sedimenting drift by 48 %, always with respect to the bottom line reference sprayer. The mean coverage in the canopy was around 50 % with both sprayers, showing a similar distribution in the canopy.

Key words: Airblast sprayer, precision agriculture, noise, power consumption, deposition, spray distribution, drift, losses.

Introduction

Citrus are one of the most important crops in the world with a yearly production of 131 million tonnes. Spain is the sixth largest citrus producer and premier exporter of fresh citrus worldwide (FAOSTAT, 2017). One of the most common methods of protecting citrus against pests and diseases is the use of Plant Protection Products (PPP). In citrus orchards, pesticide applications are usually carried out using airblast sprayers, also known as atomizers. They deliver the spray in a radial way and are assisted by turbulent air currents generated by fans on the sprayer. However, during pesticides applications several associated problems can occur. Large quantities of spray volume and airflow are fairly common today without properly adjusting the amount of product to the actual needs and specific conditions of the application (vegetation to be treated, pest to be controlled, pesticide used and machinery). This practice normally entails an excessive release of products that remain in the food and pollute the environment, with the consequent pesticide risk for fauna, flora and humans (Gil&Sinfort, 2005; Derksen *et al.*, 2007; Cunha *et al.*, 2012; Garcerá *et al.*, 2017), and also increase crop production costs. Moreover, the fans of airblast sprayers produce environmental noise, that can affect people both physically and psychologically (Durgut and Celen, 2004). Fans are also responsible for high gasoil consumption that increases the cost of the PPP treatment.

With the EU Horizon 2020 project *Healthy crop, Healthy environment, Healthy finances through Optimization* (H₃O[®]), Pulverizadores Fede have developed a completely new generation of sprayers that adjust airflow and recommend spray volume in accordance with the characteristics of the canopy and the treatment (pest and crop).

The aim of the presented study was to assess the efficiency of this new generation of H₃O[®] sprayers, in citrus crop with emphasis on *power consumption, canopy spray distribution, noise contamination, and potential drift losses*.

Materials & Methods

H₃O[®] Smartomizer overview

The most notable physical features of the H₃O[®] S3.0 sprayer (Figure 1) are, on the one hand, the aileron in the top of the nozzle channels that allows the adjustment of the spray profile to the canopy profile, and on the other hand, the fan, which can be adjusted mechanically both in the angle of the blades and the aperture of the air output channel. Moreover, this intelligent Cloud connected atomizer is fitted with a Global Position System (GPS) and temperature and relative humidity sensors. Especially, intelligence and Internet/Cloud connectivity make it the first of a completely new generation of sprayers that have been named Smartomizers.

The H₃O[®] S3.0 Smartomizer works with custom made software, installed on a tablet that controls the Smartomizer wirelessly via a Wi-Fi connection. The software recommends a spray application volume and an airflow rate depending on the characteristics of the orchard (Tree Row Volume (TRV), tree and row spacing, hedgerow vs. isolated trees configuration), and the characteristics of the treatment (internal vs. external). Based on the recommendations of the software, the user selects the nozzles to get the recommended spray application volume at a selected advance speed and with a working pressure between 8 and 15 bar. During the spray application, working pressure is automatically adjusted depending on the real-time measured advance speed to change the water flow in order to obtain the recommended spray volume. Regarding the recommended air flow, prior to the application, the fan system is automatically adjusted by changing the angle of the fan blades (20° / 25° / 30° / 35°) and the aperture of the air output channel (110 mm / 130 mm / 150 mm). During the mixing of the products, the system measures ambient temperature and relative humidity to determine if the conditions are appropriate for the intended spraying application. During spraying application, the tablet mounted in the tractor's cab allows real-time control of spraying parameters such as pressure, and forward velocity. It also displays proactive warning messages, should application parameters differ from the intended. After the spraying application, the GPS and Internet/Cloud connection allow treatment analysis from the back office, and spraying data is securely stored in a Cloud database to allow for full treatment traceability.

Figure 1. H₃O® S3.0 Smartomizer.

Experimental orchard

Field trials were carried out in a commercial 19-years-old ‘Clemenules’ mandarin (*C. reticulata*, Blanco) orchard (39°26'30.06"N 0°33'12.05"W), with a tree and row spacing of 6.3x2.8 m. Row direction was North-South. Trees averaged 2.75 m in height, 3.20 m in diameter along the row, and 4.41 m in diameter across the row (calculated as the mean of ten randomly selected trees of the orchard), which gives a mean canopy volume of 20.32 m³/tree (calculated as the mean of ten replicates considering citrus canopy as an ellipsoid with the tree dimensions). Trees were grown over raised beds, with an average height of 56 cm. Even so, due to the high volume of the trees and the way they have been pruned, lower branches facing the path hung over the path and almost touched the ground (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Aerial view and detailed picture of the orchard.

Treatments and applications description

Two treatments were compared: (1) *Standard treatment* (ST) following the indications of the orchard technician, applied with the reference sprayer Fede Futur 1000L 2005 and (2) *Adjusted treatment* (H3OT) following the recommendations of the H3O[®] software, applied with the H3O[®] S3.0 Smartomizer. Applications were repeated three times with each sprayer, alternating each one of them.

Both ST and H3OT treatments were set up simulating a treatment to control California red scale (*Aonidiella aurantii*, Maskell), which means that the treatment should cover the total canopy, in an orchard with tree rows configured as hedgerows. Both sprayers were fitted with standard, disc and core conic nozzles, model 1553 (Hardi International A/S, Nørre Alslev, Denmark), with black core (hollow cone). Flow rate of each treatment was manually adjusted by selecting nozzle disc sizes to get the corresponding volume rates at a working pressure of 10 bar.

The spray parameters used for ST are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Spray parameter for the Standard Treatment (ST).

Spray volume (l/ha)		Advance speed (km/h)	Water flow (l/min)	Working pressure (bar)	Air flow (m ³ /h)
Theoretical	Real				
3700	3820	1.59	63.77	10	92859

The set up for the H3OT is shown in Table 2. Based on the spray volume recommended by the H3O[®] software, the nozzles were chosen and their orientation was manually adjusted. Since recommendations related to the airflow rate in the tablet are indicated through the blades angle and the aperture of the air output channel, real airflow rate and air speed were measured.

Table 2. Spray parameters for the H3O[®] treatment.

Spray volume (L/ha)		Air			Mean advance speed (km/h)	Mean water flow (L/min)	Mean working pressure (bar)	
Theoretical	Real	Theoretical Blades angle	Air output channel aperture	Measurements Flow (m ³ /h)				Speed (m/s)
3520	3465	25°	150 mm (minimum output speed)	66336	26.18	1.59	57.84	10

Each application consisted of spraying the spray solution in two central paths of the orchard, with both sides of the sprayer opened, simulating an application in which the sprayer goes up and down every path. The spray was applied along 50 m of each path. Spray solution consisted of a mixture of water and a fluorescent tracer, Brilliant Sulphoflavine (BSF) (Biovalley, Marne La Vallee, France), at a concentration of around 1 g/L.

During each application, meteorological conditions were taken from the Godelleta weather station (39°25'14.7"N 0°40'38.3"W, 270 m altitude) belonging to the Valencian Irrigation Technology Service (STR) network (available at <http://riegos.ivia.es/datos-meteorologicos>). Applications were made targeting temperatures between 5°C and 35°C, and wind speed between 1 and 3 m s⁻¹. Meteorological conditions during the application of each treatment are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Meteorological conditions during the applications (mean values).

TREATMENT	Predominant wind direction*	Average wind speed (m/s)	Average temperature (°C)	Average relative humidity (%)
ST_1	SW	2.34	11.3	49.67
ST_2	SW	2.62	16.78	57.69
ST_3	SW	2.98	16.77	58.93
H3OT_1	SW	2.69	13.3	44.45
H3OT_2	W	3.01	13.3	69.54
H3OT_3	SW	3.07	18.13	55.46

*Row direction was North-South

Efficiency assessments

The *power consumption* (W) was determined by measuring the tractor's Power Take-Off (PTO) revolutions (rev per min) and torque (Nm) with a torque sensor (model TM-215, MAGTROL Inc., USA) fitted to the PTO during the spray applications.

Once in the laboratory, power consumption (W) was calculated with the following expression (Equation 1).

$$Power (W) = \frac{Torque (Nm) \times PTO speed (rev per min)}{9555 \times 1000} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Noise contamination (dBA) was measured in one point at 100 m distance from the trial area and at 1.5 m height from the ground during the spray applications. A-weighted sound pressure level (dBA) was measured with a sonometer (model SLM-1352A, ISO-TECH, UK) directed towards the application area with a frequency of 1 Hz, set in fast mode and fitted with a protective hood.

Once in the laboratory, the A-weighted equivalent sound pressure level (LAeq) was calculated as (Equation 2),

$$L_{Aeq} (T) = 10 \log \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T 10^{L_i/10} \times t_i \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where L_i is the A-weighted sound pressure level (dBA) taken in the second t_i , and considering the whole measuring time coincident with the application, T ($\sum t_i$).

Canopy spray distribution was assessed by means of *percentage of coverage on leaves* (%). Coverage was estimated with Water Sensitive Papers (WSP) placed in 18 quadrants (three heights, two depths and three widths) (Figure 3) of the half canopy in three randomly selected trees of the central row for each sprayer. Inside each quadrant, two WSP were stapled onto the upper side of two random leaves and two onto the underside of two other leaves.

Figure 3. A) Side view of a citrus tree. Distribution of Water Sensitive Papers (WSP) in height. B) Top view of a citrus tree. Distribution of WSP at each height.

Once in the laboratory, the WSPs were photographed, and the images were digitally analysed with a custom made software programme. For each image, the programme calculated the coverage (%) (percentage of the total surface covered by the impacted droplets). Once the estimated coverage of each WSP was obtained, the mean coverage values of locations 1 to 3 and 4 to 6 were calculated at the three heights, thereby obtaining the mean of the coverage at two depths at each height.

Potential drift losses were assessed by estimating potential sedimenting drift and potential airborne drift.

Potential sedimenting drift was assessed by pieces of blotting papers (73 g/m² filters. ANOIA S.A., Barcelona, Spain) located at ground level in three adjacent paths at each side of the two central paths.

Potential airborne drift was measured with nylon threads (Model Star. Golden Fish fishing lines. Efectos Navales OCAÑA S.L., Pontevedra, Spain) with 2 mm of diameter and 9.0 m long, located in the next adjacent path at each side of the two central paths. After the application, the threads were cut into sections of 1 m length.

Collectors were picked up after each sprayer pass and stored under dark and fresh conditions. Once in the laboratory, collectors were washed with de-ionized water to extract the BSF deposits. A sample of each resulting washing water was analysed for quantification of the BSF concentration by fluorometry (fluorometer model Cary Eclipse. Varian Instruments, California, USA). The amount of spray deposited per unit surface of collector ($\mu\text{l}/\text{cm}^2$) was calculated from the reading of the fluorometer, taking into account the volume of washing water, the BSF concentration in the tank, and the surface of the corresponding collector.

Results

Power consumption was much lower with H3OT than with ST (Table 3), with a percentage of reduction of 55.45%.

Noise contamination was much higher during ST than during H3OT (Table 3). The H3O[®] sprayer produced 15.20 dBA less than the reference sprayer.

Spray distribution in the canopy was similar with both sprayers, regardless of height and depth of the tree and the side of the leaves (Figure 4). In general, as expected, coverage was higher on the outside of the trees than on the inside, and in the middle and bottom heights in comparison with the top height. Mean coverage was also similar for both treatments (Table 3).

Figure 4. Percentage of coverage in different parts of the canopy depending on the treatment.

Table 3. Mean values of power consumption (W), noise contamination (dBA), and coverage (%) for each treatment.

Variable	ST	H3OT
Mean power consumption (W)	36946.43	16458.22
Noise contamination (dBA)	68.34	53.14
Mean coverage (%)	52.8	53.5

Potential sedimenting drift was lower for H3OT in almost all the paths. As expected, it decreased as the distance to the sprayed paths increased in both treatments (Figure 5). If deposits on the central paths (paths 1 and path -1 in Figure 5), on which the sprayer advance, are not taken into account, the ground received almost 48% less deposits with H3OT. If the same spray volume would have been applied with both sprayers, the reduction would amount to 42%.

Figure 5. Potential sedimenting drift ($\mu\text{l}/\text{cm}^2$) in the ground of each path of the experimental site depending on the treatment.

The potential airborne drift profile was similar for both treatments, with similar values and shapes (Figure 6). The great height of the trees with respect to the sprayers and the small distance between the sprayer and the vegetation might have confined the spray between the trees and this could explain the small differences between treatments for heights up to 7 m. Furthermore, in both treatments the upper zones received much larger deposits than the lower zones, and the thread at 1 m height received higher deposit than the following ones. This

reflected the size and shape of the trees, because the dense vegetation of citrus constitutes a great resistance to the spray movement driven by the air flow generated by the fan, and droplets rose over the trees and passed under them.

Nevertheless, H3OT potential airborne drift decreased with height after reaching a maximum value at 6 m, but it did not decrease for ST, which could indicate that with ST the spray cloud showed a more vertical movement due to the lack of deflector in the reference sprayer.

Figure 6. Potential airborne drift ($\mu\text{l}/\text{cm}^2$) profile at each side of the central paths depending on the treatment.

It can be summarized that the H₃O[®] Smartomizer reduced the power consumption by 55 %, the noise contamination by 15 dB, and the potential sedimenting drift by 48 %, always with respect to the bottom line reference sprayer. The potential airborne drift was not reduced. The mean coverage in the canopy was around 50 % with both sprayers, showing a similar distribution in the canopy.

In conclusion, with H₃O[®] a commercial highly efficient airblast sprayer was designed, good for resource-efficient eco-innovative food production as well as for food producers' competitiveness. Intelligence and Internet/Cloud connectivity make it the first of a completely new generation of sprayers called Smartomizers.

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